

The *Tusu* Festival and Kudmi Identity: Ecogender Dimensions of Culture and Agriculture in Bordering Regions of Jharkhand and West Bengal

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***Abstract:** Kudmi community is an agrarian community. They are deeply rooted in their land and also followers of the principle of Jal (water), Jungle (forest) and Jamin (land). This community mainly resides on the common border area of Jharkhand and West Bengal. There are many similarities among the people of this border area in terms of cultural and social aspects. Most of the socio-cultural activities are observed according to agricultural activities. The agricultural cycle follows a seasonal cycle and many cultural activities of the Kudmi community like fairs and festivals are celebrated by balancing these two, the agricultural cycle and the seasonal cycle. Their festivals like Bandna, Akhayan Jatra, Nawa Khai, and Tusu are closely associated with agriculture. Tusu festival is one such festival that is closely linked with the agricultural activities of the Kudmi community. Goddess Tusu is worshipped in Poush Mas (mid-December to mid-January) as Goddess Lakshmi, the goddess of food, wealth, and prosperity. This paper would deal with the ecogenderism perspective of the Tusu festival of the Kudmi community. This paper will focus on the ritualistic aspect of Tusu worship. It would also show how it entwines agriculture and the culture of the Kudmi community in Jharkhand and West Bengal border area.*

Keywords: *Tusu* festival, Kudmi community, Agriculture, Culture, Ecogenderism.

Introduction

“*Baro mase tero parban*” is a popular proverb of West Bengal. Its literal translation is thirteen festivals in twelve months. Actually, it refers to the idea of celebration, a celebration of daily life, a celebration of all seasons, a celebration of God’s grace and the supreme power of nature. All these celebrations are celebrated in form of festivals or *parab* or *parban*, rituals, lok-kathas or folk narratives. In Jharkhand also there is a similar and popular proverb among Adivasis, “*tera mahina pe tera gana*” or thirteen songs in thirteen months. It is said that all rituals, lokathas and cultural descriptions of Adivasis are found in these lyrical and oral forms those are transmitted from generation to generation. The age-old tradition is narrated through these songs. Community members, nature, ancestors, spirits, gods and goddesses are part of the tribal and Kudmi pantheon. Therefore song plays a prominent role in the festivals of tribal and Kudmi people. Samar Basu Mullick opined about Adi dharam or ancient religion that “The creator lived with created. Therefore, life is eternal and immortal. Death is the beginning of the rebirth of life but in its inferior or superior forms. The human dies and shakes the visible existence off only to live on as a shadow in the shade adobe with the spirits of the ancestors as a benevolent spirit.” (Munda xi) This quote by Mr Mullick is quite appropriate about the ancient religion of tribal people. There is no concept of heaven and hell. Everything is on this earth where nature is only shelter and a source of tribal people’s celebration. Most of the tribal people and Kudmi community are depended on farming and forest for their daily livelihood. Wood, honey, fruits and other forest products, they get from forests and rice, wheat, and other crops and vegetables are produced by them. Here agriculture takes an important role in all Adivasi culture. Some festivals are celebrated to wade off agricultural fatigue and some are celebrations of the process of agriculture. *Tusu* festival of the Kudmi community is one such festival that deeply associates with agriculture. The word agriculture refers here mainly to paddy cultivation. A complete process of paddy cultivation takes almost half of a year and most of the food is based on rice or processed

form of rice in this region, therefore, it is the most prevalent crop in agriculture. Many rituals are performed amidst the process of paddy cultivation from sowing to harvesting and woman plays an important role in this paddy cultivation. Here ecogenderism perspective can be defined. Kudmi families coexist with tribal society and create harmony as a neighbouring brotherhood relation. Nature is too close to them that their wealth is marked by the owned amount of cattle and land of paddy cultivation. Therefore the whole process of paddy cultivation plays an important role in the Kudmi community.

Kudmi Community

Kudmi community is also called as mahato, kudmi mahato, mahanta or kudmi mahanta community. This community is an aboriginal peasant community. The Kudmis, agricultural community had a tribal status till 1921 in British India. Later they transformed into a fringe caste of the Hindu and at present they are identified as OBC or Other Backward classes. There are many similarities between the Kudmi people and the tribals of Jharkhand. In terms of culture, lifestyle and religion faith all have a shared connection between them. Kudmi people still believe in animism and spirit worship. The concept of gramthan¹, village Sarna² or sacred *Sal* grove is prevalent in both Kudmi and tribal culture. “Although the Mahathos are regarded as a non-scheduled Hindu caste, today in 1921 census they were reported as a Scheduled tribe. Earlier anthropologists like Risley (1951) have cited the Kurmi-Mhatos of the former Manbbhum district as a typical case of a hitherto tribe transformed into a Hindu caste.” (Mahato, 44) There many movements are still going on for their socio-political status against the government of India. The homeland of this community is traceable in some parts of Chatanagpur³ and adjoining regions of West Bengal, Jharkhand and Odisha. They prefer to reside on the bank of rivers and it is still defined as the territory that is surrounded by the broader rivers’ banks, Damodar, Kangsabati or Kansai, Subarnarekha, Bhaitarini and tributaries of these rivers.

Fig. 1. Kuiry, Hare Krishna. Border rivers' banks.

Being residents of the river banks, favourable tropical weather and appropriate geographical location of the Chotanagpur plateau the peasant, Kudmis prioritises paddy cultivation as agriculture. Most of their rituals, cultures and traditions take forms surrounding the process of paddy cultivation and related agricultural activities. An agricultural festival like Akhayan jatra is the first day of the agriculture year of the Kudmi community. *Rohin* is celebrated for the first day of paddy seed spreading on paddy fields. Then *Karma* festival is celebrated with paddy seedlings. *Sohrai* or *Bandna* festival is a thanksgiving festival to animals and agricultural artefacts for a good harvest and finally, in the whole agricultural process, the *Tusu* festival is a year ending festival. It is a harvest festival that is mainly celebrated by the Kudmi community. Goddess *Tusu* is worshipped as Goddess *Lakshmi*. This festival is also celebrated by Santhal, Munda, Kharia and Ho in Jharkhand and West Bengal.

Goddess *Tusu*

Goddess *Tusu* is the centre of the *Tusu* festival. There are many opinions about the origin of the word *Tusu*. *Tusu* word may have

been derived from the word *tush* which means paddy rind. According to Dr Sukumar Sen, it may have been derived from Tisya star that relates to the brata ritual of unmarried girls in Bangladesh (Karan 199). This festival is one month long festival from *Aghan Sankranti* to *Poush Sankranti*. *Aghan* or *Aghrahasan* is the eighth month of the Bengali calendar and *Poush* or *Push* is ninth month of Bengali calendar. *Sankranti* word denotes the last day of a month. This festival is observed from mid-December to mid-January according to the Gregorian calendar. *Kartik*, the seventh month of the Bengali calendar and *Aghan* are quite busy months for farmers because it is the time to harvest the paddy crop from the fields. Before *Aghan Sankranti* farmer finished harvesting and placed the last clump of the rice plant on *Khola* or *khamar*⁴. That clump is called *Dini Budhi*, *Dini Giran* or *Dini Thakrain*. It is believed that when the ritual of *Dini buri* is accomplished Goddess Lakshmi or Goddess *Tusu* enters the farmers' house.

Fig. 2. Kuiry, Hare Krishna. Dini Buri/ Giran/Thakrain, Patjhalda, 29 Dec. 2022.

The process of *Tusu* installation is interesting. First, *sara* or a particular type of earthen plate is covered with rice powder and *kharimati* or calcareous soil. Then one ball of cow dung is placed on it. Vermilion, *akanda* or giant calotrope flower and marigold flowers are put on that ball. This process is called *Tusu pata* or *Tusu* installation. The installation process varies in regions. Then Goddess *Tusu* is invited and nurtured during the whole month through evening song and at last she is immersed at the nearest river, pond or water reservoir. Kudmi women bring *Chodal* from the local bazaar and worship that *Chodal* as Goddess *Tusu*. *Chodal* word comprises two words *chou* and *dal*. *Chou* means four and *dal* means something that is used for swing. Therefore *Choudal* refers to a colourful paper decorated wooden or bamboo frame that has four legs or holding points and is carried by swinging. This *Choudal* is a symbolic representation of Goddess *Tusu*. *Tusu* songs are the most important part of this festival. Through songs, *Tusu* is installed, invited, nurtured and immersed. During this one month, *Aghan* to *Poush Tusu* festival gets rhythm with *Tusu* songs, sounds of *dhenki*⁵ and aroma of *pithas*⁶. Finally, it ends on the day of Makar Sankranti.

Fig. 3. Kuiry, Hare Krishna. Chudal and villagers. Tuss festival, Uhatu, 14 Jan. 2021.

Ecogenderism Perspective

Ecogenderism is a developing theory that is a part of deep ecology. The term ecogenderism is a compound form of two words, ecology and gender. Ecogender Studies is a new theoretical framework that elaborates on gender roles in society and opens a new nexus between environment and gender. There are many concepts relating to this concept of ecogender like ecoperson, greener gender, ecofeminism and so on. All these concepts link human beings and the environment and in this particular context of the *Tusu* festival, ecogender relation presents a strong bond between nature or environment and women. Here eco gender gap enters where females are prioritised over male. Though it sounds stereotypical notion the fact is that sensitiveness about nature more goes toward the female gender and maybe that is one reason to call nature mother nature. Ecology and gender are intertwined. In the indigenous, Adivasi, Kudmi community or any others culture there are certain duties those are shared between men and women. It beautifies their traditions also. The distribution of gender roles and the gender contribution in Kudmi society can also be found in this *Tusu* festival. First *Tusu* is considered Goddess *Lakshmi* or *Poush Lakshmi*. As this festival ends in *Poush* month and Lakshmi is the Goddess of food, wealth and fertility. Therefore *Tusu* festival symbolises the field fertility. *Tusu* songs are an important part of this festival. Its flexibility, tone, and composition are very attractive and fascinating. *Tusu*'s worship, invitation, installation, care, nurture, awakening and immersion are done through singing *Tusu* songs and gradually Goddess *Tusu* becomes a family member of Kudmi community. There is no specific *mantra* to worship the Goddess *Tusu*. *Tusu* song is the only way to invoke or express gratitude towards *Tusu*. Goddess *Tusu* is not always considered a goddess. Sometimes she is treated as a mother, sometimes as a companion, sometimes as a bride and sometimes as a daughter. During this one month mid-December to mid-January, Goddess *Tusu* is treated as an intimate member of the family. All these beautiful relations with Goddess *Tusu* are expressed by women through *Tusu* songs.

Bela uthe riti riti, pirthibi alo kiore

Emni alo kiorbe Tusu, e khela kadamtale. (Das Mahato 50)

As the Sun rises up in the sky, we can see the colour of the beautiful earth.

Same as we (Women) enjoy the beauty of *Tusu* when she plays under the kadam (burflower) tree.

This couplet of *Tusu* song describes the beauty of human relations. Here Goddess *Tusu* is treated as a little girl or daughter. She loves to play the whole day with her friends under the Kadam tree and the women of the village love to see her playing. The untouched beauty of the rural landscape, the presence of a beautiful sunrise, kadam tree and the mother's affection can be felt through these lines. Mother-daughter relation is drawn through these lines of *Tusu* song.

Jal jal je koro Tusu, jole tomar ke ache?

Monete bhabiyeen dekho, jole shwashur ghar ache. (Das Mahato 54)

Tusu, why are you becoming restless and always mentions about water,

tell me who is there?

Now I recall that your father-in-law's house is there.

Here Goddess *Tusu* is treated as a companion who is asked by her mate about their father-in-laws' house. Married Goddess *Tusu* is too hurrying to go to her abode that is in water. Her fellow beings tease *Tusu* mentioning her father-in-law's house. Here immersion of Goddess *Tusu* draws a sad tone. In that case, women try to find an answer to the separation from *Tusu* and they get to console themselves by thinking about *Tusu* and that *Tusu* will return again to her own land from her father-in-laws' house that is a water body. The relationship between ecology and gender is

emphasised in each couplet of *Tusu* songs. Separation and hope for reunion both are described through these lines. Kudmi people are much aware of the miracle of nature, the germination of seed and therefore they also believe in rebirth. Birth and death are nature's laws so Kudmi women says goodbye to *Tusu* through immersion in water and at the same time, they wish to meet her next year with the same enthusiasm. Here environment and women or nature, goddess and human are not separate from each other. They are so close and cohabit with agriculture and culture.

Hamra je Tusu thapi, aghan sankraite go

Tel dilam, sailta dilam, swarge dilam bati go.

(Das Mahato 48)

We install Goddess *Tusu* on Aghan Sankranti or the last day of Aghan month,

We put oil, we put cotton,

And we offer a lighted earthen lamp in heaven for Goddess *Tusu*.

This lyric of the *Tusu* song is dedicated to Goddess *Tusu* as a mother or protector. The narrator worships goddess *Tusu* by lighting the earthen lamp. The simplicity and conversational tone of *Tusu* songs express many emotions of rural women. As *Tusu* is treated in many relational forms like a companion, daughter, protector mother or goddess, women share their happiness, grief, excitement and with wishes with Goddess *Tusu*. Here sharing of feelings intersects with gender and nature.

Another Eco gender relation can be found at the very first installation of Goddess *Tusu* on Aghan Sankranti and then singing songs at dusk. It shows the caring nature, responsibilities and creative minds of women. As many *Tusu* songs' lyrics are composed instantly so it is an example of creativity also. Eco

gender relation is a thin perspective but it presents the overall folk culture, rituals of Adivasis and traditions of the Kudmi community.

Conclusion

Dr Pashupati Mahato states that the tone of *Tusu* is echoed in the air of villages. It is quite relatable in that one-month period mid-December to mid-January of the *Tusu* festival because throughout the month *Tusu* songs are sung by women. These *Tusu* songs are primarily transmitted from generation to generation. It also shows that it is a part of age-old culture. It can be said that these songs are the voice of the rural Kudmi people. Sometimes it is also used as the protesting voice against social injustice. These songs intersect Kudmi people with nature, community members, gods, goddesses and ancestors. It also helps to keep them grounded and helps to work in their agricultural fields. One couplet of *Tusu* song that is sung at the time of the *Tusu* installation emphasises the relationship of ecology, gender and the importance of agriculture or paddy cultivation in the life of the Kudmi community.

Khamar bhara sonar dhane Tusu patiba jatane

Aigo tora sangijuri Tusu pati ek mane. (Candra Rajak 157)

All my dear fellows come and do join in the process of *Tusu* installation,

We install Goddess *Tusu* at our *Khamar*

that is full of golden worthy paddy with our complete devotion.

In these lines, paddy is compared with gold. Therefore it also signifies the importance of agriculture and its dependency. Kudmi people especially women's conviction on Goddess *Tusu* as a protector of crops or as a Goddess of wealth, fertility and wealth is also expressed through these lines. The word *Sangisathi* (all fellow beings) refers to inclusiveness and communal bonding.

Greeting with complete devotion shows the spiritual connection between women, gender and ecology through these lines.

This festival connects the whole community and gives a space for celebration after winding up the agricultural activities and a linking line can be drawn that links gender roles, agriculture and the *Tusu* festival of the Kudmi community in Jharkhand and West Bengal border area.

Notes

1. Gramthan: Gram means village and than is place. Gramthan is a sacred place where village deity or gram debata resides.
2. Sarna: Sarna means shelter. Sanrna is a sacred grove where saran maa or Goddess or mother Sarna resides.
3. Chotanagpur: It is a plateau that covers most of the area of Jharkhand and adjacent part of Chhattisgarh, Odisha, West Bengal and Bihar.
4. Khola or Khamar: *Khola* or *khamar* is a colloquial word that refers to a clean space to keep paddy straw and it is also used as a threshing field of paddy
5. Dhenki: a wooden log that is used to husk paddy rind or to make rice powder.
6. Pitha: Pitha is a kind of dish that usually made from rice flour similar to pancakes or dumplings.

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